
Smart Health Care Monitoring System Using Arduino

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Abstract: According to polls, over half of the world's population (7.3 billion) dies as a result of a poor health monitoring system, i.e. the inaccessibility of hospitals and physicians to all patients at all times of the day. In the current scenario, this condition affects around 20% of the population. We know that even a single minute may make a difference in life-or-death situations. So, to address this issue, the remote health monitoring system is proposed. This issue has been the focus of medical professionals as well as IT professionals for a long time. The proposed system comprises sensors to monitor both heart rate and body temperature, which are both critical. Along with this, a real-time server using an Ethernet system and the user interface are integrated to alert the system for daily observation.

Keywords: Healthcare monitoring system, IoT, Arduino, Sensor

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

With a quick google search, the current world population is 7.9 billion by the year 2020, China is the first with 1.4 billion and followed by the second most populated country India 1.38 billion, and the rest big countries like the USA also contribute to this ever-growing number. According to the World Health Organization, the life expectancy of most people is 60 years and beyond. Later by 2050 the life expectancy of people is reduced by a huge number. The reasons are very simple, with the increase in age of the person, different health problems arise. According to a fact sheet provided by World Health Organization, "The world's biggest killer is heart disease, responsible for 16% of the world's total deaths. Since 2000, the largest increase in deaths has been for this disease, rising by more than 2 million to 8.9 million deaths in 2019. Stroke and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease are the 2nd and 3rd leading causes of death, responsible for approximately 11% and 6% of total deaths respectively"[1].

1.2. Motivation

Health is the primary element of the human need for a better life. Unfortunately, there are a lot of diseases that are unpredicted and impulsive, like heart attack, stroke, cardiac arrest, etc. Only immediate action can be a blessing for life at the last moment [2]. But every time people are not so fortunate as this, various reasons lie inadequate health care services, the nonexistence of good transport links between rural and urban parts of cities may be unavailability of good medical facilities, doctors, and caretakers for the need of patient [3]. Here modern technology with the help of IoT and communication systems plays a big role. Numerous assisted technologies have been developed for elderly people which can be manually handled by the patient itself or by a doctor placed at a remote location. For a more accurate assessment of the vital signals of the patient, there is a need for advanced sensors. One of the vital human signs in any critical or emergency situation is measuring

Pulse or Heart BPM which can be measured at any position of the body by firm contact on the wrist or near the neck region of the patient. And the other one is temperature, as a 2 or 3-degree Fahrenheit deflection can indicate health problems in a patient.

In these situations, a remote health monitoring system (HMS) plays an important role in enabling contact-less and distant health-data exchange. This reduced the traditional methods for health monitoring improving health management and significantly reducing cost and time. For a personal home environment, these don't create any problems as they do not comprise security and privacy levels but also provide a user-friendly with easy configuration [4]. The advancements in IoT technology provide an advantage on these technologies. IoT doesn't mean communication between two devices but rather it helps in proacting and collecting data, which can also be stored in a cloud so that be processed and later reviewed by professionals. This M2M is a fast energy efficient, far more intelligent, flexible, and interoperable method for remote health monitoring systems, which is also in a stage of improvement. Various big companies like Intel, Arduino, Raspberry, etc. are investing a large amount of money in this technology. Thus, an IoT connects patients, doctors, hospitals, personal caretakers, physicians, and emergency services under the HMS.

1.3. Objective

The proposed work is based on this model: a lightweight device that can be able to read the vital sign of a human patient in a fraction of seconds but also helps in communicating the idea among a specified group of people. Generally, these devices are costly to manufacture and very few companies have manufactured them at low cost using crowd funding. Most HMS manufactured available in the market are expensive and also limited to only a few sensors due to market business strategies [4]. The proposed model allows users for an effective monitoring system for patients with the help of IoT to allow cost margin for communicating and collecting bio-data from sensors and hardware with an effective low cost and allowing in high efficiency. And also, with the help of cloud computing, the data collected can be beneficial for various stakeholders in this ecosystem. The proposed system will provide the data using a Wi-Fi module to a cloud platform; later this data can be cleaned and processed for better visualizations. In the case of an emergency or critical point of the patient, it can trigger an alarm to alert whoever is in charge of the ward or someone close to the patient.

2. DESIGN

A HMS consists of hardware and software design; where the hardware part deals with the working and making of the electric and electronic circuits and the software part deals with the programming of the Arduino micro-controller (in c programming) and a smartphone (Fig. 1). An application is made to show the real time data using android studio.

Fig 1: Flow chart design

2.1 Modular Description

I. Arduino Micro Controller - The Arduino chip is a micro-controller board that is based on the microchip and it is used by people to build projects and electronic kits.

Fig 2: Arduino Uno

It has digital and analog input/output pins that can be connected to diverse expansion boards and different circuits. It contains everything required to support the micro-controller; merely connect it to a laptop with a USB cable or power, it with an AC-to-DC adapter or battery to urge start (Fig. 2).

II. Temperature Sensing Element - A temperature sensing element is used or we can say a sensor, which when touched, will give the output temperature in centigrade.

Fig 3: LM35 Temperature Sensor

This has 3 terminals that sense surrounding temperature and has a range from $-55\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Fig. 3). It is even more precise than a thermistor output device.

III. Pulse Sensor - A pulse sensor has a LED on the front surface and sensors (which sense pulses) are on the backside. A person has to place his/her finger on the sensor, and the LED will blink a bright light which easily gets passed through the skin of a human and it gets reflected by the arteries and veins in the human body.

Fig 4: Pulse Sensor

There is a small hole in the center of the sensor through which light travels and then on the sensors attached behind the LED. The sensors send the data in form of an analog signal to the Arduino board. Below the LED, there is a noise elimination circuitry that is supposed to keep away the noise from affecting the readings (Fig. 4).

IV. ESP8266 Wi-Fi Module

Fig 5: Wi-Fi Module ESP8226

The ESP8266 is a circuit made on a chip, manufactured by a company called 'Espressif'. It gives us Wi-Fi communication, so that we can use it to connect to a Wi-Fi network, then connect it to the internet, and let any kind of smart device (like smartphones, smart-watches, and more) connect to this board so we can monitor and see all the data that has been collected by sensors (Fig. 5).

V. 16x2 LCD Display -

Fig 6: 16X2 LCD

An LCD is a kind of module that displays a visible image using liquid crystal. It has the maximum ability to display 16 characters in 2 lines as shown in the Fig. 6. In most of the Arduino embedded systems, this LCD is used to make the interface user-friendly and it also gives Arduino programmers the liberty to customize the code according to needs.

3. Implementation

3.1 Methodology

The model designed (Fig. 7) shows the working of HMS. When a patient touches the temperature and pulse sensors, the sensors measure the pulse rate and temperature of the human body. Then the Arduino software starts analyzing and processing the code and displays the result on the small 16X2 LCD display unit. ESP8266 Wi-Fi module is used for sending the data to the cloud server of the device using its Wi-Fi communication functionality. Thingspeak is open-source software that allows its users to communicate from anywhere in the world to an internet-operated device with convenience. We can analyze the data from any part of the globe by just logging in to the 'Thingspeak' channel and we can also use certain functions there to analyze the data more properly.

Fig 7: Complete circuit.

3.2 Communication

There are various protocols in communication that are being used today to give easy connection between smart devices. These protocols of communication offer various services through different smart devices (whether heterogenous or homogenous), ability to connect to other devices and provide different services to the community for the betterment. Different examples of these protocols of communication are Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, RF (Radio Frequency Network), Ethernet, and cellular connectivity [5].

3.3 Processors

Processors are the area where the computation processes are done and are a very important part of the IoT system. It is also said that these two entities (processors and software Applications) are the brain of an IoT network. Communication Processing units consist of different hardware platforms available like Intel Edison, Arduino, IBM Watson, Raspberry PI, Beagle Bone, Intel Curie, etc. And these can be available in any form like microprocessors, micro-controllers, or in SOC (System on Chip) form. Other than these, many other platforms are known for providing good IoT services also. Cloud platform services is also one of the most frequently mentioned and used service. It allows many smart devices to send important data remotely through its cloud services. And then from the availability of the data from the cloud, the data can be fetched from any part of the world. And yes, this fact remains that, even though the data can be fetched from any part of the world at any hour, the data can be processed and analyzed in real-time also. Then the processed data can be used by the user, medical professionals, or anyone, who has authorization to the data and can be used for any benefit. Also, cloud platforms are available for free as well as paid (they differ in functions and services), in our work we have used Thingspeak which is a free open-source platform.

3.4 Services

IoT itself has many services. It does all the functions that are necessary and that have to be done on the data it receives and analyses. And the decision-making is also improved by the use of artificial

intelligence and machine learning algorithms. IoT is not just applied in the technological field, instead, it is used in many different fields like agriculture, dairy, food engineering, and so on so forth. This shows that IoT provides so many services to its users with only one goal and that is to provide diverse functionality.

3.5 Methods for Scalability

Scalability issue arises when a very big amount of data is being generated and collected somewhere. For example, in a hospital the data of many patients like their beats per minute (BPM), body temperature, Blood pressure (BP), and different reading are generated and collected in the database for analysis, it's a difficult thing is manage all of that data. Hence there should be a proper method to receive, transfer, and analyse the data coming from patients to get the proper state and report of the patient and to maintain accuracy in the system [6-8].

3.6 Working Principle

START

step 1: Power is switched on.

Step 2: press both the sensors, the pulse reader, and the temperature sensor using a finger.

Step 3: wait for results on the LCD.

Step 4: If an error is shown press the restart button. Otherwise follow step 5.

Step 5: Open the Thingspeak. And check the value shown in the graph.

STOP

4. Advantages and Improvements

The recent global pandemic COVID-19 has affected millions of lives across the globe in the most disastrous ways possible but it has also taught something to all of us. One of those things that we have learned from this pandemic is that the world is not ready for this kind of emergency in near future. Talented doctors and qualified staff are required globally. But that is not it, there is also the requirement of the availability of the technology that can support the medical staff and reduce their burden. The modern HMS is one of those techniques which the world can rely on [9,10].

4.1 Advantages of the HMS

- **Prioritization of Patients-** HMS is really helpful for the doctors to prioritize their patients in the case of an emergency which eventually helps the patients needing urgent care.
- **Convenient** - It is easy for the doctors to monitor the patients with just one app.
- **Portability-** Patients can carry the device with them which makes it easier for them to monitor their health anytime and anywhere.
- **Treatment availability-** In the emergencies like COVID-19, it will be helpful to treat large numbers of patients as the number of patients will be far more than the number of doctors required.
- **Utilization of the resources-** HMS helps the hospitals to utilize their resources and money more wisely.
- **Saving time and money-** HMS reduces the requirement for individuals to visit the hospitals very often which eventually saves their time and money.

- **For the Chronic Diseases-** Since most chronic diseases are incurable, it is important to monitor the state of the patient all the time. HMS is helpful to monitor chronic diseases and respond in the case of an emergency.
- **Prevention-** The biggest advantage of the HMS is that it helps to follow the most basic but important principle of life i.e. “prevention is better than cure”.

4.2 Future Improvement

1. This device can be connected to a computer terminal and analysis of the data in real-time can be carried for better diagnosis.
2. The device can have a system to display any abnormality if found in the collected data.
3. Even various sound effects can be added to represent different functions and results to make it more user-friendly.
4. More health monitoring parameters to be measured like ECG, EEG, EMG and BP etc.
5. The overall structure and design of the system can be improved to make it more durable and efficient.

5. Current Issues and Research Directions

5.1 Privacy and Security Issues

There are two more things that IoT has to handle (privacy and security) of the user and the other end where the data is being sent for any purpose. If no proper algorithm to protect data is applied, then the data can be leaked, lost, altered, or can be fetched by unauthorized people, and thus can be misused by them. So, it is important to maintain the confidentiality of the user's data. That is why it is advised to use proper authenticated ways to login into the system to maintain privacy. All the confidentiality protocols should also be followed. And we all know the IoT is all about transferring data, so getting leaked can be a very common phenomenon. So, everything related to the user to be kept private and should be secured by using proper methods and algorithms.

5.2 Storage Issues

Storage in IoT is an integral part because all the data coming from the users is going to be stored somewhere, and that somewhere is the server. In these cases, missing data or duplication of data is a very common thing. This leads to storage issues. That is why proper storage techniques should be used to store data by removing replicated data.

5.3 Energy Efficiency

Most sensors are battery-operated (in our case it can be powered on using Arduino Uno's USB power connection) but in this data generating process, power efficiency is an important factor to be taken care of. So, to save energy few techniques can be used like wake-sleep scheduling, one-time usage limit, and power-efficient batteries can also be used for further advancements.

6. Conclusion

In this work, an IoT-based mobile HMS is developed. The work also covers the importance and fruitful benefits of the implementation of IoT in mobile HMS. The human temperature and heartbeat signal is captured as the data signals and processed by the micro-controller which sends the data to

the mobile app using a Wi-Fi shield. The processed data is shown in the android application which is further stored in the server database. Furthermore, the paper also highlights the challenges involved while sensing, analyzing, and predicting the disease. The advantages of the modern HMS on a large scale have also been included to highlight its daily importance. The present work clearly shows that we have a long way to go in the field of the modern HMS by mentioning its future scope of the improvements. Also, the implemented device can be used to assist medical practitioners to do their work efficiently and without any difficulties.

7. References

- [1] E. P. Kerr et al., "Sensor-based Vital Sign Monitoring, Analysis and Visualisation for Ageing in Place," 2018 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN), 2018, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/IJCNN.2018.8489526.
- [2] S. P. Korres, A. Menychtas, P. Tsanakas and I. Maglogiannis, "A low-cost IoT-based health monitoring platform enriched with social networking facilities," *2018 IEEE International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications Workshops (PerCom Workshops)*, 2018, pp. 173-178, doi: 10.1109/PERCOMW.2018.8480186.
- [3] S. Chaudhury, D. Paul, R. Mukherjee and S. Haldar, "Internet of Thing based healthcare monitoring system," 2017 8th Annual Industrial Automation and Electromechanical Engineering Conference (IEMECON), 2017, pp. 346-349, doi: 10.1109/IEMECON.2017.8079620.
- [4] M. Bansal and B. Gandhi, "IoT Based Development Boards for Smart Healthcare Applications," *2018 4th International Conference on Computing Communication and Automation (ICCCA)*, 2018, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/CCAA.2018.8777572.
- [5] P. W. Digarse and S. L. Patil, "Arduino UNO and GSM based wireless health monitoring system for patients," *2017 International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems (ICICCS)*, 2017, pp. 583-588, doi: 10.1109/ICCONS.2017.8250529.
- [6] A. Nduka, J. Samual, S. Elango, S. Divakaran, U. Umar and R. SenthilPrabha, "Internet of Things Based Remote Health Monitoring System Using Arduino," *2019 Third International Conference on I-SMAC (IoT in Social, Mobile, Analytics, and Cloud) (I-SMAC)*, 2019, pp. 572-576, doi: 10.1109/I-SMAC47947.2019.9032438.
- [7] Ramesh Saha, Biswas, S., Sarmah, S. *et al.* A Working Prototype Using DS18B20 Temperature Sensor and Arduino for Health Monitoring. *SN COMPUT. SCI.* **2**, 33 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42979-020-00434-2>.
- [8] Salem, Osman, and Ahmed Mehaoua. "A Secure Framework for Remote Healthcare Monitoring using the Internet of Medical Things." *ICC 2022-IEEE International Conference on Communications*. IEEE, 2022.
- [9] Bora, Pronami, et al. "Smart real time health monitoring system using Arduino and Raspberry Pi." *Materials Today: Proceedings* **46** (2021): 3855-3859.
- [10] Manasa, K., and S. China Venkateswarlu. "A Wearable Health Monitoring System Using Arduino and IoT." *2021 3rd International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communication Control and Networking (ICAC3N)*. IEEE, 2021.